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Public Transportation Infrastructure Projects and Financial Risks

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ABSTRACT

When implementing a public transport infrastructure project, there are always a number of financing risks that need to be addressed before any such project is embarked upon. One of these risks concerns traffic demand/revenue risk – the envisaged public transport system needs to attract patronage; this requires private car users to make the switch to the alternative mode of transport. This would also be the case for the various public transport infrastructure projects that are being investigated to alleviate road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), Lebanon, as alluded to in this article.

1. INTRODUCTION

Successful private-sector funded public transport infrastructure projects are those projects that are able to meet financial commitments and provide private participants their required rates-of-return. The ability to meet financial commitments is a direct result of the establishment of proper financial and project structures. Establishing the proper structures results from identifying key project risks, then creating structures and policies that mitigate those risks.

2. PRINCIPAL RISKS IN FINANCING PUBLIC TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS

The principal risks involved in financing public transport infrastructure projects can be categorized into (Estache & Strong, 2000; Schwartz et al., 2006):

- construction-phase dangers; and
- start-up and operating phase risks.

2.1 Construction-related dangers

During the construction phase, the major risks are:

- *Delays in project completion and the commencement of project cash flows* can result in an increase in total costs through higher capitalized interest charges. It may also affect the scheduled flow of project revenues necessary for debt servicing costs and operating and maintenance expenditures.

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- *cost overruns with an increase in the capital needed to complete construction.* For a variety of reasons, including incorrect engineering and design, increased material and labor costs, and project start-up delays;
- *Contractor insolvency or lack of experience: The main contractors and key subcontractors should have the experience and reputation, as well as the financial, technical, and human resources, to complete the project on time and within budget.*

Further, the risk of non-availability of materials or equipment for construction or operation exists, especially in many developing countries. This is especially true with respect to specialized equipment. Also, environmental and land risks may cause delays. Public transport infrastructure projects can have a substantial environmental impact. Such projects frequently attract strong opposition from community and environmental groups over issues of pollution, congestion, and visual impact. Similarly, land acquisition can be a protracted process with the potential for extensive legal delays, particularly in developing countries. Furthermore, the cost of land acquisition can become a major factor where land values have risen rapidly or are subject to speculative activity over which the project developer has no control. In these cases, agreement on some form of cost ceiling may be necessary in the concession contract.

2.2 Start-up and operating phase risks

The major risks for public transport infrastructure projects during the start-up and operating phase are:

- *Technology risks:* project financing participants cannot ignore new technologies since they can significantly improve the profitability of a project. The use of obsolete technology may adversely affect a project.
- *Financial risks (interest rate and foreign exchange rate fluctuations):* since the advent of financial crises in emerging markets, few projects are able to generate returns-on-investment sufficient to attract private capital. This suggests that until macro-economic risk premiums decline and traffic demand is more established, only a limited set of projects will be undertaken without substantial government support. The financial crisis may force many programs to slow down and force debt restructuring of many of the existing concessions. Since the risk of bailouts is high, there is a need for more secure financing structures.

Another financial risk is driven by the impact of fluctuations in foreign exchange rates on the value of the business. This is a major issue for some projects, where revenues are commonly in local currency and adjustments for inflation and foreign exchange rates may lag or encounter political opposition.

- *Force majeure risks:* force majeure refers to risks beyond the control of either the public or the private sector, such as flooding or earthquakes, which impair the ability of the project to earn revenues. The rule is that if there is a risk of force majeure, the contract should say what happens if that happens.
- *Regulatory and legal risks:* regulatory risks stem from the weak implementation of regulatory commitments built into concession contracts but also in laws or other legal instruments relevant to the value of the transaction. The question to be asked is whether the regulator will exercise its authority and responsibilities over prices, public obligations, and competition rules, as well as other rules that are specified in the contracts and influence the value of the business. Because, even if regulatory rules are clear enough, they are only as effective as the regulators can be.

Legal risks entail the fact that, typically, project financing structures cover periods of ten years or more. However, over that time period, the relevant legal and regulatory environment is likely to change substantially. The rules governing the financial consequences of these changes between the

government, users, and operators are critical, but they are frequently overlooked. The rules must allow for changes to the contract terms during the time that the project is being funded.

- *Governments* generally agree to compensate investors for political risks, although in practice, justifications for government actions may be cited to delay or prevent such payments. Thus, private investors generally assume the risks associated with dispute resolution and the ability to obtain compensation should the government violate the concession agreement. The issue of meeting financial obligations while disputes are resolved may be achieved through a requirement for debt servicing reserves, contingency funds, or standby financing.

Political risks concern government actions that affect the ability to generate earnings, such as actions that terminate the concession, the imposition of taxes or regulations that significantly reduce the value of the business for investors; placing restrictions on the ability to collect or increase tariffs; precluding contract disputes from being resolved in reasonable ways;

2.3 Traffic demand/revenue risks

Unlike project financing in other sectors, take-or-pay or fixed-price contracts are typically not available in public transport infrastructure projects, so traffic demand risk is a major issue in virtually all of these projects. Even when there is a reasonable level of confidence in forecasts, traffic demand can be dramatically affected by competition from other modes or facilities, changing usage patterns, and macro-economic conditions. These inter-related issues, over which the project sponsor often has little or no control, are very difficult to predict and represent a major risk to financing. In particular, traffic demand forecasting during the early years can be quite subjective. To the extent that these risks are driven by economic conditions, there is a potential role for the government to play in risk sharing, either through traffic demand, revenue guarantees, or other forms of support.

3. ATTRACTING PRIVATE-CAR USERS TO BECOME A PUBLIC TRANSPORT PATRON

For any newly implemented public transport system, it is of great importance to attract patronage. This would also be the case for those that are under study to solve the dire road traffic congestion situation in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) in Lebanon, where currently no efficient and reliable public transport system is in place. Most commuters use their private cars to get to/from their places of work or education. In this respect, it is worth noting that over 24% of employment opportunities in Lebanon are located along the Beirut-Jounieh (Tabarja) corridor, and that the majority (78%) of commuters travelling on this route use their private cars; the remaining 22% use taxi (van) services, and (mainly private sector) minibus/bus services that do not really provide scheduled services. All this road traffic on the Northern Corridor, in addition to that on the Eastern and Southern Corridors, lies at the source of the dire road traffic congestion situation in Beirut, which is such that up to 70% of commuter travel time is lost in delays due to the said road traffic congestion situation. The average reported inter-modal road traffic speed is 11 km/h (calculated as the weighted average speed across all modes), with an average speed of 9.4-13.5 km/h for private cars, 6.5-9.3 km/h for buses, 7.5-10.8 km/h for minibuses, and 8.6-12.3 km/h for taxis. As a result, every day, commuters are forced to spend hours stuck in traffic jams and in their cars, struggling to somehow reach their respective destinations.

As noted in previous articles (e.g. Choueiri, 2014, 2018, 2020, 2021a), studies to implement an efficient and modern public transport system to alleviate road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) have been underway for several years now, but are struggling to make much progress due to the various political, economic, financial, and other crises Lebanon is currently plagued with.

Among these studies, railways are also being looked at, such as revitalizing (using the already existing rights-of-way) railway services on the routes (see Map):

- Beirut-Jounieh-Tabarja-Maameltein (Tripoli); and
- Tripoli-Abboudiyeh.

3.1 The SkyWay option

Another option being considered is to build an elevated SkyWay system between Beirut Rafic Hariri International Airport and Casino du Liban (Jounieh), with intermediate stations at strategic locations (Aoun et al., 2019; Choueiri, 2021b), which could achieve significantly shorter travel times than a private car (see Figures 1 and 2). Travelling by private car from Beirut-Rafic Hariri International Airport to Casino du Liban in Jounieh, a distance of 49.7 km, takes about 1 hour and 50 minutes. However, as can be observed from the table below, when travelling by the SkyWay system (average travel speed of 100 km/h), which would have a shorter route of 40 km (10 km shorter than the road alternative), the travel time would be just 30 minutes (this figure takes into account a travel speed of approximately 5 km/h when passing through the intermediate stations, as people would embark and disembark, which would take about 1 minute per station), see Table 1.

Figure 1. Beirut-Jounieh SkyWay Investigated Alignment and Station Locations on Google Earth Basemap

Figure 2. GIS Simulation of the SkyWay Investigated Alignment and Station Locations

In order to meet Ynitskiy's (or Unitsky's) standards, a minimum radius of 1,000 meters was considered for the entire project, resulting in an acceptable speed of 100 km/h along the entire alignment on straight and curved sections (Aoun et al., 2019). In the Unitsky String Technologies (UST) system architecture, a distinction was drawn between two types of support. Every one kilometer, an anchor or tensioning support is employed; the second type is an intermediate support, which was employed to alleviate the sag effect/vertical deflections on the structure. Based on the clearance required from the bottom of the unibus and the travel path below, the typical height of each support erected on the ground is 10 meters above the roadway level and 18 to 25 meters above sea level. There are 43 anchor supports and 1,285 intermediate supports in total on the planned route.

Table 1. Travel Time Comparisons between Personal Vehicle trips and the SkyWay Technology

Origin-Destination	Length - Personal Vehicle (km)	Time - Personal Vehicle (mins)	Length - UST (km)	Time - UST (mins)
Beirut Airport - Raouche	10.6	27	10.037	6
Raouche - Zeitouna Bay	5.5	23	4.441	3
Zeitouna Bay – City Mall	10.2	23	7.363	4
CityMall - Le Royal	9.2	11	7.310	4
Le Royal - Military Club	6.2	10	5.736	3
Military Club - Casino	8.0	17	5.183	3
Total	49.700	111 (1 hr 51 mins)	40.070	30 mins

3.1.1 Cost Estimation

Table 2 shows a summary of the project's costs.

Table 2. UST Construction Cost

Item	Unit Price (USD)	Number of Units	Total Cost (Million USD)
610UB152 Beam	1,555.50	1328 pieces	2.07
502CHS12.1 Column	1,656	1328 pieces	2.20
1000x7000 Pile	1,705	1328 pieces	2.26
35 mm Cable	37	480840 m	17.79
Concrete	75.50	2172.89 m ³	0.16
Materials (Extra)	750	1328 pieces	1.00
Construction Labor	2,996,540	40.07 km	120.07
Terminal Stations	4,167,251	2 pieces	8.33
Intermediate Stations	100,014	5 pieces	0.50
Traffic/Site Management	1,048,789	40.07 km	42.02
Design and Commissioning	111,279,093.36	9%	10.02
Land Acquisition	-	-	5.28
Total	-	-	211.70

3.1.2 UST Feasibility Study Results

When public transportation is well-established, driving a private automobile during rush hour becomes a luxury rather than a necessity. As a result, people who choose this level of luxury will pay a higher price in tolls, parking fees, and congestion costs. The following are the key findings from the feasibility study for the UST Project:

3.1.2.1 Ridership Potential

This system may create an average yearly revenue of \$3 million if ridership is between 3,000 and 4,000 per day, which is comparable to an average of 1,280,000 people per year, depending on fare price.

3.1.2.2 Implementation Costs

A UST project system costs \$211.7 million in total (see Table 2), or \$5.3 million per kilometer. As a result, when compared to the expenses of other forms of transportation, this system is extremely cost-effective.

3.1.2.3 Energy Consumption

The UST cableway has a low energy demand of 1.8 million kilowatts per year. Users who shift away from automobile trips result in lower GHG (Greenhouse Gas) and carbon emissions. The more the system expands, the higher the commuter trips that result in lower additional emissions.

3.1.2.4 Comparative Analysis with Other Modes of Transport

High speed, high efficiency, and low rollout cost are the fundamental characteristics of a UST system. Figure 3 highlights comparisons with various modes of transportation in terms of capital costs, pollution, operational costs, and traffic accident rates.

Figure 3. Comparison between Transport Modes Regarding:
 a) Capital Expenses, b) Environmental Pollution,
 c) Operating Expenses, and d) Traffic Accident Rate

SkyWay vs. Cableway (Dunayeva & Vinakurava, 2019)

The principle of the cableway is the movement of the cable, on which the cars are fixed, between two points. In SkyWay, the vehicle (electric rail vehicle) is not moving along a cable that requires regular replacement every 6–8 years, but on a steel profile. When moving at the same speed, energy consumption in the string railroad will be 5–6 times lower compared to the cableway.

SkyWay surpasses the cableway in a range of parameters – operating costs, service life, safety, speed, performance. It is worth noting that SkyWay, in contrast to the cableway, has various types of tracks, making it possible to combine them, and a wide range of vehicles.

Table 3. SkyWay vs. Cableway

Characteristics	Cableway	SkyWay
Speed	21.6 km/h (6 m/s)	Up to 150 km/h (in city)
Track length	Up to 10 km	Unlimited
Principle of movement	Outboard motor moves both cable and cars	Autonomous steel-wheeled
Turning capability	No	Yes
Service life	Complete replacement of cables each 6–8 years	Track structure: 50–100 years; Rolling stock: 25 years
Safety	Low	High
Comfort	No climate control	Climate control
Cost effectiveness	Low	High

SkyWay vs. LRT (Dunayeva & Vinakurava, 2019)

Compared to LRT, SkyWay vehicles' capacity is much more attractive than that of the Light Rail Transit (LRT).

Table 4: SkyWay vs. LRT

Characteristics	LRT	SkyWay
Rolling stock capacity	Train: from 4–5 cars from up to 100 passengers each. Platform length: minimum 150 m	Coupled unibuses: up to 240 people on the upper track and up to 175 people on the lower track. Platform length: up to 50 m
Headway	From 1–2 minutes	From 20–25 seconds
Safety	Medium	High

SkyWay vs. Monorail (Dunayeva & Vinakurava, 2019)

Compared to monorail, SkyWay wins primarily in terms of speed. In addition, monorail requires a very massive overpass, with high material capacity.

Table 5: SkyWay vs. Monorail

Characteristics	Monorail	SkyWay
Track length	Up to 50 km	Unlimited
Rolling stock capacity	Train: from 4 cars for up to 80 passengers and more each. Platform length: minimum 100 m	Coupled unibuses: up to 240 people on the upper track and up to 175 people on the lower track. Platform length: up to 50 m
Maximum speed	70 km/h	150 km/h
Principle of movement	Elevated pneumatic-tired transport	Autonomous steel-wheeled vehicles
Headway	5–20 minutes	From 20–25 seconds
Service life	Track structure: 50 years; Rolling stock: 10–15 years	Track structure: 50–100 years; SkyWay rolling stock: 25 years

3.1.2.5 Funding Opportunities

Because the UST system is both creative and cost-effective, it is an excellent contender for funding. Local improvement districts, public and private partnerships, as well as state, federal, and local transit enhancement programs, could all be feasible funding sources.

3.1.2.6 Traffic Assessment Impacts

By 2050, the urban population in Lebanon is expected to have grown to 87 percent of the overall population (Khoury, 2017). Such rapid expansion would result in increased traffic congestion, increased traffic accident risks, and unreliable public transportation systems. Furthermore, the domination of private passenger automobiles would result in overcrowding on current roadways, higher GHG emissions and pollution levels, and higher total mobility costs. Without UST, all existing public transportation modes in Lebanon would result in just unorganized traffic, which would have a negative impact on global warming, mobility, cost safety, and social productivity.

By all accounts, the UST System has the potential to attract a large number of travellers, as 29% of people now use public transportation (Khoury, 2017). Traffic volumes would be reduced by 3,680 vehicles per hour during AM times (4417 passengers) and 2,925 vehicles per hour (3,510 passengers) during PM periods, based on a carrying capacity of 12,200 per day and an occupancy of 1.2 individuals per car. The number of cars would be reduced by 8,362 (10,034 passengers) during AM periods and 6,644 (7,973 passengers) during PM periods if 65.88 percent of residents considered using the UST system.

3.1.3 Project Impact Assessment

Adopting some form of public transportation is, without a doubt, the most consistent, safe, and convenient choice. However, because Lebanon's road space and land area are limited, allocating a bus lane would almost surely worsen traffic congestion. In this regard, the UST elevated railway transportation system avoids issues like road space and uses only 1.8 kilowatts per year, demonstrating its excellent environmental friendliness (Yunitskiy, 2015). The O-D (Origin-Destination) speeds clearly

illustrate that this technology is far faster than a car and easily avoids all traffic bottlenecks. In terms of cost, the UST is a viable option when compared to other modes of transportation, costing roughly \$8 million per 1 km of construction with a 50% contingency. Furthermore, UST's zero-tolerance policy is highly effective.

3.1.4 *Project Disadvantages and Limitations*

Every public transportation system offers a set of advantages. However, some disadvantages may arise as a result of the UST system's implementation; these are listed below:

- The most challenging issue in any public transportation system is funding and regulatory policies.
- Pile foundations necessitate a high level of precision, which could drive up building costs.
- Relevant stations necessitate site space and regulatory approvals for land acquisition.

As a result, more comprehensive soil research and geotechnical studies would be required to reduce the aforesaid disadvantages, and regulatory requirements would need to be examined to avoid any on-site operational risks.

3.2 **SkyWay – a commuter survey**

With respect to the SkyWay option, a survey was held among 306 current commuters in Beirut aimed at gathering their viewpoint on their current use or non-use of public transport and to acquire an insight into whether they would be inclined to use the SkyWay system should it become available. Amongst other things, the results of this survey yielded the following (Aoun et al., 2019):

- 238 (78%) of the respondents regularly used the private car as their primary mode of transport, 148 (62.18%) of them would consider shifting from travelling by private car to travelling by SkyWay system should it become available;
- 61 (20%) of the respondents used some form of public transport (taxi (van) services, and (mainly private sector) minibus/bus services), and a negligible proportion used other modes of transport (bike and motorcycle);
- 203 of the respondents earned less than \$1,500 per month, 116 of them spent \$100-\$300 (7%-20% of their monthly income) on transport each month. From these 116 respondents, 96 (82.76%) used the private car as their prime mode of transport. Further, 56 of the respondents travelled by bus. Of those travelling by bus, 52 (92.8%) had an income of less than \$1,500 per month (39 (75%) of them spent less than \$100 on transport each month). These figures seem to suggest that, despite their low incomes, the respondents prefer to use their private cars;
- 41.07% of the 56 respondents who travelled by bus spent about 30-60 minutes from home to their respective places of work/education. Of the 238 respondents who travelled by car, 108 (45.38%) also spent 30-60 minutes to travel from home to their places of work/education. Both modes of transport get stuck in the same traffic jams;
- 111 (33%) of the respondents ranked travel time to reach one's destination as their first priority for choosing a mode of transport. For this reason, 81 (73%) of them would consider using the SkyWay system which, as noted earlier, would offer very favorable travel times, as an alternative option. Thus, travel time would be a major criterion for using public transport.

It has been estimated that the SkyWay system which, as noted earlier, could offer more favorable travel times than the private car on the route Beirut-Jounieh (as it passes over all traffic congestion obstacles), could attract some 3,000-4,000 passengers per day, which would be equivalent to an average of 1,280,000 passengers per year (Aoun et al., 2019). In view of the low car occupancy rate of 1.2

persons/car in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) (Kadi, 2016), this could lead to a significant reduction in the number of cars circulating on the roads.

3.3 Attracting private car users to become public transport patrons

For any public transport system to be conceptualized to accommodate a reasonable level of ridership on a given corridor, it is essential that the system specifically understands, targets, and adapts itself to the current private car users. Once an objective has been established, it can then be carried out through respective levels of subsidy as well as fare and price discrimination mechanisms.

To attract current private car users, the majority of whom would be middle-class professionals, to patronize the public transport system, it should be recognized that one of the key variables, besides the price of tickets, would be the location of stations. Also, in suburban areas, the stations would need to have adequate parking facilities as the majority of commuters would need to park their cars at the station and then use the public transport system to commute into the city. As for stations in Beirut, it would be very important to address the issue of transport mode transfer, as well as to consider the walking distance from the station to the Central Business District or other destinations in the city. For instance, requiring a commuter to use three modes of transport to get to his/her place of work would likely diminish ridership. Noteworthy in this respect are the two following comments that were made by respondents to the SkyWay survey (Aoun et al., 2019):

- If SkyWay coincides with my time and destination, it will be my choice; otherwise, I will use my car.
- There is also the comfort criterion! If it is a hassle to use SkyWay, then I would still consider using my car.

4. FINAL REMARKS

In the various articles that have been published in this journal over the years, it has become quite clear that Lebanon, and especially the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), is in dire need of a modern, reliable, and efficient public transport system that can take commuters to their places of work and education, as well as others to their respective destinations, in a more comfortable and environmentally-friendly manner than when travelling by private car, which is so often characterized by being stuck in polluting traffic jams. A well-established public transport system would greatly enhance the mobility and quality of life of the people, as well as bring other societal and economic benefits. Once in place, people would become more and more familiar and appreciative of its many benefits, thus turning many of them into patrons of such a system.

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POST SCRIPTUM

Please note that the survey addressed in this article was conducted in 2017/2018, i.e. prior to the financial and economic collapse of Lebanon that started in October 2019, and is still continuing this very day, exacerbated even more by the current afflictions taking place in Ukraine. “Up to 90% of Lebanon’s wheat and cooking oil imports come from Ukraine and Russia, as well as a large proportion of grain imports” (citation from news item ‘Lebanese fearful as fuel and wheat shortage deepens: The war in Ukraine has left cash-strapped Lebanon scrambling for alternative sources of fuel and wheat’, Al Jazeera Live, 8 March 2022). Also, the Lebanese Pound has lost some 90% of its value against the US Dollar, which also puts the income figures noted in the article in a different light. Furthermore, as the price of gasoline has gone completely out of control, also exacerbated by what is presently going on in Ukraine and the various restrictions that are in place, only a very small proportion of people can afford to travel to their places of work/education (these days, the price for 20 liters of gasoline stands at \$300-00, i.e. \$15-00 per liter, to put it into perspective).

Remaining hopeful that, one day, things will get back to normal, solving the issue of the dire road traffic congestion situation in Beirut, either by implementing a ground-based railway system or an over-ground SkyWay system (see opposite page), should remain high on the agenda. It is assumed that, once in place, commuters will soon see the advantage of a modern, reliable and efficient public transport system that can take them to their places of work/education in a passenger-friendly, relaxed and comfortable manner – quite the opposite from the stressful daily battle to get to one’s destination (see opposite page).